

Editorial

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Habits of research: five practical contributions to research training

The editorial, we would like to share with you five habits that have made our research careers very important existential moments in both the personal and collective dimensions, because each of the people who have contributed here with these editorial also does so from an important place in the scientific ecosystem. In this order, the reader will find in this editorial, which will take a little more space than the one that was written, a set of habits that we invite you to read in the key of, a researcher has as a habit: “Use selection criteria of a scientific journal”, “Implement technological tools for the management of research profiles”, “Search for scientific literature in research”, “The document of memories or exegesis as a habit in research creation” and “Write collective texts”.

Using criteria for selecting a scientific journal

One of the tasks that should be considered as initial when starting the process of writing a scientific article is related to the selection of the scientific journal to which the document is to be sent. This would avoid rework when adapting the document to the requirements of the journal; as we know, each journal has its own requirements and, in many cases, if we choose it when the article is finished, it is often necessary to adjust some elements or reorganize them according to what the journal expects in terms of structure and content.

There are many recommendations on the elements to consider for the selection of the journal, namely: subject matter, peer review process, quality, language, speed, open access, costs and even the respective review in the list of predatory journals, however, these elements could be grouped into 4 basics points:

1. Subject matter/editorial line/Call for papers: it is important to be clear about the subjects that the journal publishes.

There are even journals such as *Profesional de la Información* that inform about the topics they do not publish so that it is clear to whom they intend to send a document. Many journals work based on calls for papers, so it is important to check whether the document is related to the call for papers and the deadlines for receipt.

2. Internal processes/periodicity/standards: it is important to check if the journal states the deadlines for initial review, peer review, deadlines according to its periodicity (in case it is not continuous) and this is directly related to its standards and requirements, everything requested must be sent to avoid rejections due to lack of documents. These deadlines give the author an idea of how long the process will take and the documentation required. There are journals that quickly inform whether the article will go through the peer review process or not and give the author the possibility of being able to redirect it to another journal.

3. Indexing: there are countries and institutions that require researchers to publish their research in journals that are indexed in specific databases or indexes. Before submitting the document, it is important that the researcher checks whether the journal meets the requirements to avoid wasting time in the process. The most internationally recognized indexers are Scopus, WoS (Clarivate Analytics) and Scielo.

4. Costs: there are institutions that have budgets for publications and in others it is the researcher who must cover the costs, so it is important that the researcher verifies that these costs can be covered and that it is a journal accepted by the institution, as there are often predatory journals that charge and are not indexed.

There are support tools on the web that help with these reviews, such as [Think-Check-Submit](#), which provides a series of guidelines for the researcher to review before submitting an article.

Large publishers also have systems that help them locate journals by placing the abstracts of your paper and some additional data, such is the case of [Springer](#), [Elsevier](#), [Taylor and Francis](#), among others. The author can also review white lists of journals, the most recognized is [DOAJ](#), although in Latin America there is [Latindex](#).

In any case, experience in the submission of documents provides the researcher with personal tools that are perfected over time and

that allow them to make more accurate submissions and have more controlled processes within their area of knowledge. There are also consultancy companies that provide support with these processes, which is recommended when the researcher is inexperienced and needs to be accompanied in these processes. In any case, carrying out the submission process requires dedication and patience.

Implementing technological tools for research profile management

Undoubtedly, with the development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), the processes of scientific publication have undergone a remarkable transformation, including: greater accessibility and increased production. During this large amount of information on the Internet, scientific journals, in order to increase the number and visits of readers, increase citations of published articles and achieve a solid academic visibility, require, together with the implementation of an editorial strategy, the knowledge and use of metadata to be properly located by search engines (SEO).

Currently most journals implement the Open Journal System (OJS) platforms, an automated editorial management system, which incorporates the Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) protocol that facilitates interoperability in the transmission of metadata in electronic format on the Internet; in these journal platforms, authors must complete various metadata relating to the proposed article.

On this occasion, reference will only be made to the ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) code, a persistent identifier known throughout the scientific community (PID). Although this task of reviewing metadata is part of the editors' responsibilities, researchers must take the correct completion of the metadata seriously, as the quality of the metadata will determine, to a large extent, their visibility in the networks, both as an author and as an article, as well as the speed of the publication process. For publishers, the "correct" name is the one declared in their ORCID code record.

From the author's experience, it is notable the number of proposals received with little correspondence and carelessness between the declaration of the names on the platform, when making the submission, and the names of the records of their ORCID codes (names and surnames complete in lowercase letters, appearance

or omission of orthographic accents, omission of middle name and second surname, etc.); even in the absence of this important persistent identifier; as well as between the declaration of the names that appear as authors in the OJS platform (generally only the author responsible for the correspondence) and the names declared as authors of the contribution received in the file. Another aspect to highlight is the non-disposal, by the researchers, of the data from the ORCID code records to the public and the non-completion of their academic credits in said profiles.

This ORCID code metadata does not appear as mandatory in the OJS platform, so the above aspects should be clearly reflected both in the Instructions to Authors and in the Checklist of submissions; since “an empty ORCID or one that is not interoperable with other resources does not make much sense”.

It is therefore necessary to recommend to researchers that they complete the data in their ORCID code profiles correctly, with the help of their CVs, and keep them up to date. This allows, among other things, that there is no confusion between authors with the same name or ambiguity when the author uses one or two of their names or surnames, as well as consistency when making connections with digital tools such as Google Scholar, ResearchGate and even the more recent Clarivate author profiles.

It is important that the appearance of the publications made, if they are numerous, the use of the Publish or Perish (PoP) software is suggested, where the results of the search and saved in BibTex format can then be imported into the ORCID code profile of the researcher in question.

The promotion of the use of this code, not only in articles, but also in email signatures, business cards, posters, electronic presentations, academic social networks and incorporating them into QR codes, is a pending task.

As mentioned at the beginning, this is the responsibility of the editors, but cooperative work with the epistemic communities is necessary, which are interpreted not only with the members of the editorial board of the journals but also with the scientific councils, scientific societies, Research, Science and Technology departments, among others. This work should include liaison or subject librarians, who are essential in information literacy work. All this work contributes to good practices for scientific communication and open journal publishing, which will make the journals more open in compliance with the FAIR principles and more visible.

Searching for scientific literature in research

In the context of what in modern times has been called “scientific culture”, and very particularly in research training, the habit of adequately searching for scientific literature in databases and various sources of information that are appropriate to the type of research that one wishes to initiate plays a role of capital importance. The success of the research work undertaken depends to a large extent on this search to avoid certain theoretical, conceptual and methodological ambiguities and inaccuracies.

On the other hand, as we all know in recent decades, the Internet has substantially transformed the way in which both teachers and students undertake the search for scientific literature, which is of paramount importance to provide a foundation and good epistemological and methodological foundations for the research project undertaken, whether it is qualitative, quantitative, or mixed in nature. A good researcher must know how to make an optimal exploration in recognized databases, as well as in repositories of national and foreign higher education institutions, without neglecting websites of groups and lines of research that are advancing projects or research of similar subject matter; also, reading indexed journals both physical and electronic, blogs and some social networks that go along the line of scientific enquiry.

It is curious that according to several scholars on this subject such as Inger and Gardner (2016), who undertook the task of surveying more than forty thousand readers from different areas of knowledge from the five continents and of different ages and academic levels, they concluded that rather little is known about the good habits of searching for scientific literature by both teachers and students who begin a research project or work. The reasons for this are of various kinds, including the lack of training for a good research culture and poor habits in terms of enquiry and bibliographic research in academic and scientific literature in higher education centers and particularly in centers or departments dedicated to scientific and teaching research.

It is interesting to note that, in the research carried out by the two previous authors, a certain preeminence is still given to searching in bibliographic databases of journals and specialized books according to the specific disciplinary area, followed by academic search engines and some aggregator services such as ProQuest, JStor and EBSCO. On the other hand, in the academic field, Google Scholar is more widely used in several countries, even over Google itself, especially in the social sciences, medicine, life sciences, agricultural sciences and economics.

As for institutional repositories, it can be said that they are gaining strength, especially in countries that are positioning their higher education institutions in the sphere of high quality accreditation, which implies a greater demand in the references made by teachers and students of bibliographic references based on theses, research papers, academic texts and modules from various disciplines that have already been uploaded to these platforms with a certain guarantee of academic monitoring, assurance that they have undergone anti-plagiarism programmes and have been the result of unpublished work that contributes to the theoretical body of work of the discipline or science in question.

About the use of mobile devices, especially mobile phones and tablets for research enquiry, it has been increasing significantly; in the same way, the use of applications on these devices to access the storage and reading of articles and books derived from research has grown significantly in recent years, especially since the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020.

In summary, it can be corroborated how there are still many challenges and in terms of good habits for researching scientific literature by teachers and professors; particularly in higher education, adequate training is required to improve these research habits and thus optimize the good search for scientific literature that will lead to an optimal research process. It is the task of HEIs in the country and in the world to provide better training tools for students and teachers so that, in addition to the traditional bibliographic consultation databases, they are provided with various possibilities of accessing information and communication technologies that are in line with the development of science, knowledge and the most up-to-date scientific knowledge to establish a dialogue with classical and traditional knowledge.

The document of memories or exegesis as a habit in creative research

Habit is understood as behavior that, through repetition, is incorporated into the being and that in its constant practice seeks to form virtuous people (Gómez, 2010). In this way we propose a strategy for research-creation such as the habit of systematizing what is observed as the process progresses, a systematization in progress in a document of memories or exegesis. That is to say, the document is researched and designed as it is made, not before as in the classical scientific method.

For those of us who are in artistic practice, and in many cases stage practice, it is very difficult to draw up a document that demonstrates or explains how we arrive at that result or shows how we arrive at the success or failure of our artistic production. Consequently, we ask ourselves how to formulate a research methodology to carry out a creative-research work? What would be the essence of this effort? Why or why defend a theoretical reflection in the practice of artistic creation? Grass (2011), from a perspective in defense of theory, proposes that documenting research-creation leaves us with three contributions: first, the possibilities of artistic endeavor as a way of knowing the world; second, the research process as a way of formalizing new tacit knowledge; and third, the writing of a research report as a task that allows, develops and drives reflection and establishes a dialogue with the past and the present (p. 26).

Theorizing, therefore, is nothing other than leaving a trace of what has been thought, and artistic creativity has much to offer. In this way, we propose as a habit that each researcher should design a “document of memories or exegesis” containing: 1) Ideas or questions that generated the creative process. 2) Ordering these ideas and expressing them (in a written and creative manner). 3) Examine and describe the progress of the process. 4) Write down the corrections. 5) Detail the results obtained.

This document, which can take the form of a work diary, the actor’s log, choreographic writing or phrases, direction folder, register of sketches, composition of scores, among others, will contain information on the particular way in which the observed object of study was investigated, will show the methodology used, will identify the way in which the data was collected, the ways of analyzing the documents and the route in which the results, products of the research-creation, are delivered or socialized.

In this type of research, having as a habit the “memoir or exegesis document” that records the processes and findings is essential because it constitutes the basis for analysis, study techniques are trained, doing and theorizing are put to the test. In specific cases, detecting difficulties or achievements, launching them with the creative phenomenon and critical thinking and in this way proposing something unprecedented, new, or something that was not there before and that exceeds the level of consciousness and formulates complex rationalizations. In addition, to train people who, due to their perseverance and practice, will acquire positive habits, which in the words of Gómez (2010), will become virtuous researchers.

Writing collective texts

One of the most effective habits that is important to motivate is the ability to write collective texts. Because of their ability to bring people together and write collectively, to enhance their ideas, maximizing the reach of their results, leading to important effects in the communities to which they belong.

Let's expand on the habit a little to understand why it is effective and why it is worth promoting within our research teams:

Collective writing guarantees consensus and respect for the observation places of each of the co-authors, which does not mean that we agree 100%, on the contrary, agreements are made to recognize the disagreements of the working teams. When a text is written by "several hands" as we say, it is essential to make a series of prior agreements: commitment to the development and completion of the text, the subject of writing, the time allocated to write the text, the roles of the participants, the position of each co-authorship, in order to avoid difficulties when managing the citation format, text length, mainly.

It enriches the dialogue of knowledge, contributing to the formation of values as important as respect, because those who participate in the construction of knowledge recognize active listening as a mechanism for understanding the different places of observation of those who come together. Within research practices, it is vitally important to recognize that a scientific culture is increasingly elusive in the face of collectivity, the development of collective thinking and the construction of autonomous learning environments, through the transfer of knowledge in the "learning-by-doing" action, in the evolution of research processes (Henao Cardona, & Barón-Velandia, 2022).

Increases the use of technological tools for writing, analyzing, graphing, visualizing, updating metrics, among others. Free tools for creating documents, no browser restrictions, real-time editing, version control, and simpler menus: [Typewrite](#), [Penflip](#), [YouMeScript](#), [MeetingWords](#), [StoryWars](#), [Google Drive](#), [OneDrive](#), among others.

It amplifies the dissemination of texts, of the conditions that make it possible to create communicative multipliers in the constitution of research teams. Without falling into the concept of a pyramid or business network, it is important to emphasize that it is methodologically functional to develop collective writing as it

allows people to commit to the importance of making themselves known in their various academic and scientific networks. This helps to raise awareness in direct proportion to the number of authors/contributors.

Finally, we are left as a work team, to invite you to read these five habits in research built from different perspectives and research practices that can be constituted in practical tools for training in individual and collective research, that is, they can be taken to action quickly, without theorizing, without filling us with overwhelming concepts, impossible to apply.

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